

CLINICAL SIGNS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES THAT OCCUR IN CHILDREN WITH DIARRHEA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10622810>

Annotation: This article presents the clinical signs, treatment and preventive measures that occur in children diagnosed with diarrheal diseases, symptoms of diseases of the oral mucosa in patients.

Key words: diarrhea, lactose, salmonellosis, dysentery, gastroenteritis, rotavirus, smecta, polyphepan, activated charcoal, polysorb, neosmectin, enterogel.

Diarrhea is fluid in the stool, as well as the intake of feces more than 2 times a day. This condition is a rapid movement of feces through the intestines. Diarrhea is fluid in the stool, as well as the intake of feces more than 2 times a day. This condition consists in the rapid movement of feces through the intestines. Almost all mothers have encountered cases of constipation in their children, what to do at such a time: will this condition go away on its own or should some measures be taken, but it is necessary to use folk remedies. Causes of diarrhea in children:

The factors that cause diarrhea will depend on the age of the child. Depending on the age of the child, intestinal dysfunction will be specific.

- Causes of constipation in infants:
- Formation of the intestinal system of the stomach;

- Protruding teeth;
- - Enzymatic lactase deficiency;

Constipation in breastfed children is a reaction to mother's milk, in which her milk may become low-fat or fatty if the mother does not follow a diet;

- Incorrect introduction of complementary foods;
- Switching to artificial nutrition.

External causes of constipation in children of any age:

- Poisoning from the use of low-quality products;
- When eating fruits and vegetables that soften the drink;
- Diarrhea after taking antibiotics;
- Constant stress, nervous conditions;
- Non-compliance with hygiene rules; eating dirty hands, fruits and vegetables without

washing;

- Overeating.

Diseases of the internal organs that cause diarrhea:

- Infections: salmonellosis, dysentery, gastroenteritis, rotavirus;
- Inflammation of the mucous membrane of the stomach, esophagus, intestines;
- Allergies;
- Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract: peptic ulcer, chronic colitis, enteritis, esophageal pain, pancreatic insufficiency;

- Internal hemorrhoids;
- Dysbiosis;
- Tumor diseases;
- Helminths, vomiting;
- Crohn's disease;
- Kidney failure.

This means that constipation can be caused by serious illnesses and lead to serious complications if left untreated. Diarrhea caused by children's eating habits, as well as their lack of personal hygiene, is especially common.

Based on the causal factor, the age of the child and the mechanism of cessation of diarrhea, there is a specific classification of the pathological condition. For doctors, this classification is considered favorable for diagnosis and treatment.

Any infectious disease can be: dysentery, salmonellosis, food poisoning, viral, amoebiasis. In children under the age of 2, viral constipation is also often observed in the winter season. The incubation period of the disease can last several days. It all starts with vomiting, then diarrhea, resulting in increased body temperature, severe pain in the head and muscles. The average duration is 1 week.

The main reason is a violation of the long-term diet and composition. Foods low in vitamins, food allergies and allergies to certain medications are the cause of diseases of the child's internal organs.

Defects of the digestive system – low secretion by the liver, stomach, small intestine, pancreas.

Toxic: caused by liver, kidney failure or poisoning (poisoning), diarrhea is often caused by arsenic or mercury poisoning.

Drug-induced: diarrhea caused by prolonged use of antibiotics (in rare cases, other medications). In this case, the intestinal microflora is disrupted.

Neurogenic: states of stress, intense arousal, fear, anxiety, depression.

According to the mechanism of withdrawal: hypokinetic: mushy, liquid, in small quantities, odorless stools when used, diarrhea caused by slow bowel movement.

Hypersecretory: abundant, liquid feces – diarrhea caused by an abundant accumulation of salts and water in the intestinal cavity.

Hyperkinetic: in small amounts, liquid, mushy – diarrhea caused by the rapid passage of food mass through the intestines.

Hyperexudative: liquid, watery, not too abundant, with an admixture of blood or mucus, manifested as a result of intestinal inflammation.

Osmolar: fatty, abundant, undigested food residues are formed, resulting from a decrease in the absorption of salt and water in the intestine.

In addition, according to the course of the disease, doctors distinguish between acute and chronic forms of diarrhea. However, the course of the disease is unclear, for example, diarrhea associated with tooth extraction: in some, if it lasts for several days, in some children this condition lasts until the tooth is completely removed.

Going on a trip to other places for family holidays, children develop "traveler's diarrhea". This will be due to changes in the physical factors of the weather and the external environment. After the child's body adapts, constipation returns to normal.

Clinical manifestations of constipation in children: it is believed that a well-known condition is the fact that a yellow liquid enters the child, indicating the absence of a serious pathology in the child's body. In most cases, the reason for this is changes in the stomach due to a violation of the quality of food. However, the color of liquid feces can also be different. Depending on the quality of the stool, you can guess the changes observed in the child:

Mucous mixed, watery feces - caused by an infection in the intestine, overeating, inability to digest cow's milk. The general condition of the child does not change. However, the body quickly becomes dehydrated. It is dangerous for infants.

Bloody stool: An admixture of blood to the stool is a sign of a bacterial infection. Green matter and red blood formations are observed in dysentery. Age - yellowish color-is caused by salmonellosis or E. coli infection. In a fragment of such conditions, the body temperature also rises.

Colorless chair: in infants, colorless (whitish) stools - if observed as a result of a child's reaction to breast milk-may indicate hepatitis, and in older children-hepatitis.

Green stool: if the child's stool is green, green, with a pungent odor, fever, weakness, headache, abdominal pain, vomiting are signs of infection.

Black stools: for infants on the 1st day of life, black stools are the norm, as meconium is released in it. However, in older children, the black color of the stool may indicate bleeding in the intestine or taking too many certain medications (activated charcoal, bismuth).

Foamy stools: if a child is less than 1 year old and has foamy stools, the child will have a deficiency of the enzyme lactose or dysbiosis. And in older children, foamy stools are the result of acute intoxication.

Considering the above, if a child has diarrhea, pay attention to his stool. When contacting a doctor, describe in detail the behavior of the chair. Seek immediate medical attention if, along with diarrhea, the child has the following additional symptoms:

- Nausea, vomiting;
- Abdominal pain;
- Weakness, low mobility;
- Babies do not suck breast milk and cry a lot;
- Decreased appetite;
- Sleep disorders;
- Teething in infants is manifested by an increase in the child's body temperature;
- Itching of the posterior excretory canal is a sign of internal hemorrhoids;
- Headache.
- Diagnosis of diarrhea in children

To confirm that the cause of diarrhea is not a serious disease, it is necessary to conduct a number of the following examinations: examination of feces for helminths and dysbiosis;

To study the movement of food mass in the intestine, radiography using a special porridge with barium sulfate is performed;

The coprogram;

Blood test - general and biochemical;

Ultrasound (UTT) abdominal examination;

Bacterial examination of the mass of vomit and feces, tank.ekma;

Accurate information about the infectious factor is provided by bacterial fecal culture. However, the disadvantage of this test is that it takes a long period of time, from 5 to 10 days, to get a result.

Treatment of diarrhea in children: An urgent question that many parents ask is what to do if a child has diarrhea, what precautions can we use to avoid complications? treatment of diarrhea should be aimed at eliminating the underlying disease.

Drug treatment: if a child has diarrhea, first of all, saline solutions are taken on the recommendation of a doctor, for example: Rehydron, Glucosan, Oral, Gastrolith, Enterodesis or citroglucosolan. One package of such a remedy is prescribed to be dissolved in clean water and taken orally.

With an increase in body temperature, drugs containing paracetamol are recommended. If the child is less than 1 year old, it is better to use suppositories, and those who are older can continue to take the solution, even in the form of a suspension.

The most effective drugs for diarrhea are adsorbents: Smecta, Polyphepan, activated carbon, Polysorb, Neosmectin, Enterosgel.

Symptomatic tablets for diarrhea: calcium carbonate, Diarol, Imodium.

If the cause of diarrhea is dysbiosis – Acytol, colibacterin, Biform, Linex, enterol, Bifilin, lactobacterin, bifidumbacterin, Enterogermin and other probiotics to restore intestinal microflora.

For diarrhea caused by infection, antibiotics are used that cannot be used independently, such as the drugs listed above and below, but only as prescribed by a doctor: Ersefuril, furazolidone, Nergam, gentamicin,

kanamycin, rimfampicin, Meronam, Ciprofloxacin, Ceftazidime.

Enzyme therapy - Festal, pancurmen, Pnacreatin, abomine-pepsin, Mezim forte, Creon.

Antiallergic drugs (antihistamines).

The use of antispasmodics for pain relief: papaverine, Spasmomene, Dotaverine.

Traditional medicine: if diarrhea does not manifest dangerous signs, you make sure that it does not cause serious pathologies, you can also use folk remedies to relieve diarrhea. They will help to improve the overall condition of the child:

To prevent the body from becoming dehydrated due to constipation in a child, you can use a homemade solution: in 1 liter of water, dissolve 2 tablespoons of sugar, 1 teaspoon of baking soda and salt. If the child has severe diarrhea, drink 2 teaspoons every 10-15 minutes.

You can also use plants with anti-inflammatory and antiseptic effects: blueberries, mint, chamomile, black sesame. The use of dried pear seeds. Starch solution: dissolve 1 teaspoon of starch in half a cup of water.

In the case of diarrhea in children, caution is required when using folk remedies. Especially infants may have contraindications to their use. Therefore, be sure to follow the doctor's recommendations to eliminate constipation!

In the case of diarrhea in children, it is important that parents know well what they can eat. More or less frequent meals are required. At the same time, it is necessary to reduce the amount of carbohydrates and animal fats. Dieting also pays off when diarrhea is eliminated.

Treatment of diarrhea in children should be carried out comprehensively. Medical treatment is not limited to only medical treatment, traditional medicine and diet should also be used. The diet is followed for at least 3 days after the improvement of constipation.

A complete cure for diarrhea depends on many factors. In most cases, the general condition of children worsens and negative complications arise. They may refer to:

Dehydration of the body;

Stomach disorders;

The consequences of dysbiosis are dermatitis, bronchial asthma, chronic gastroduodenitis, intestinal dyskinesia, proctosigmoiditis;

Intestinal infections can lead to neurotoxicosis, brain tumors, electrolyte disorders, infectious-toxic shock, sepsis, hemolytic-uremic syndrome, toxic-dystrophic syndromes;

Complications of dysentery - intestinal bleeding, pericollitis, arthritis, neuritis, encephalitis, hypotrophy, anemia, hypovitaminosis, pneumonia, otitis media, pyoderma;

The treatment of diarrhea that has arisen against the background of a dangerous disease is a difficult task, in which it will be necessary to eliminate the disease itself. Fluids are poured into the body to avoid dehydration.

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